

Effect of Consumer's Attitude Towards Brand Extension

Muhammad Shahzeb Fayyaz, Sajjad Nazir, Syed Muhammad Abdullah

Abstract— Since a brand launch costs heavily, so it's better to opt for brand extensions that are considered strategically more useful. The consumers have a certain perception regarding the brand name and its image; hence knowledge of consumer's attitude towards the brand is important. Therefore the present study deals with two questions; whether the parent brand helps having a positive perception towards the brand extension, and what are the initial perceptions about adaption of the brand extension. Along with this, this study has also observed the effects of the consumer's attitude towards brand extension of a renowned parent brand in three different industrial sectors, within Peshawar. Studies have shown that the indicators which affect the core brand will also have an effect on the extensions and similarly the indicators that are affecting the category of extensions will also have an influence upon the parent brand. However, the consumer's assessments of extensions in brand may sometimes change their core thinking about the parent brand that may direct to either a strong or weak positioning of brand.

Keywords— Parent brand, Brand extension, Brand image, Perception, Consumer's attitude.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the Current market scenario, a brand thought strategically is the lifeline to the success of a company. Brands make possible to proficiently instruct their well-designed and emotive values in the minds of the consumers [1]. It is a commonly known factor that new brand launch costs more therefore brand extensions are considered as strategically more useful in a company's national and international growth. To launch a new product, a Brand Extension strategy comprises of using a recognized brand name [2]. Brand image is defined as the perceptions regarding a brand as revealed by the brand association apprehended in a consumer's mind [3]. These associations submit to any feature that links the brand with the memory of the consumers [4]. Therefore in order to attain the knowledge of how consumer's attitude is towards brand extension if they have a favorable brand image of the parent brand, this study takes a balancing method to estimate. Firstly

it assess that popular parent brands paves a positive perception for a new brand extension. Secondly it also explains the initial perceptions about adaption of the brand extension due to brand loyalty. Aligned with these mentioned objective, this study is anticipated to observe the effect of consumer's attitude towards brand extension of a successful parent brand regarding in three different industrial sectors that is to observe consumer's attitude towards brand extension due to successful brand image of parent brand in related areas of Peshawar.

In the initial part of the study, a conventional essay or vital discussion rationalizing to introduce and interpret the unmitigated work on brand extension and then brand image will be presented. Followed by, stepladder used in the study and the methodology of examining information are elucidated and measures and data analysis are appraised. Accordingly, results are assessed and consequences are proposed to assist excavate the research study's objective though-out the research.

Extensions in brand include its name developed within single product group with the perspective of entering in to other one [5][6]. That scheme viewed many times as having good effects, the reason is that this decreases the obtainable price on advertisement and launching of latest brand with the chances of raising the achievement and popularity because of great liking originated by basic product worth [7]. According to [8] brand extension occurs when the firm stretches its brand in to new classes of product. He said that extensions in brand may not only help in increasing profits but also take part in penetrating and acquiring different new markets. A better scheme of brand extension is that in which the name of the brand helps the addition in the brand, where as the best extension in brand also helps in return in increasing the name of the brand [8]. Good extension in brand relay on customers understanding of homogeneity between the core brand and the new additions [9][10][11][12]. Moreover past researches discussed that the indicators which affect the core brand will also have an effect on the extensions and similarly the indicators that are affecting the category of extensions will also have an influence upon the parent brand [13][14][15][16][17]. Consumer assessments of extensions in brand may sometimes change their core thinking about the parent brand that may direct to either a strong or weak positioning of brand [18]. Brand extension strategy is very much common in fast moving consumer goods (FMCG'S) class and FMCG'S can be defined as "Those products which have fast shelf turnover rate, with comparatively low cost and do not need very much time, effort and investment to acquire", which includes product of different

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classes such as toilet items, different food products and beverages means those products which are used on a daily basis such as cold drinks, juices, soap, shampoos etc. [19]. In the category of FMCG'S and services it has been viewed that greater than 80% of the latest brands or products were launched as a brand extension and are considered as a good and profitable in the sense of reducing the cost of launching new products along with increase in the success rate [20][21][22]. Surveys conducted in United States shows that fast moving consumer goods market projects much likeness of additions in brand. It is developing with the increasing rate and became so much popular because of new introductions in products which according to some statistical figures show that launching of new brand in USA during the period of 1997 to 1984 were 120 to 175 annually out of which 60% were additions or extensions [5]. In the year of 1991, it has been seen that launches of new products were 1600 out of which 90% were the extensions [20]. In the retailing industry in 2005 launching of new products were 30,000 and the percentage of extensions were 90% [23]. Some of the best examples of brand extension in the FMCG'S category are Coca-cola which introduced apple flavor for its Fanta brand, Nestle introduced its yogurt, Pepsi also introduced Pepsi Max, Diet Pepsi, Lays etc, Gillette introduced shaving foams, shaving creams, after shave lotions, Colgate introduced different flavors in its tooth pastes and many more examples come in the domain of extensions in FMCG'S category.

According to [3] brand image is defined as the perceptions regarding a brand held in the memory of a consumer as reflected by the brand associations. On elaborating the topic further it is observed that a manager shall seldom create a set of optimistic associations of a brand in the minds of the consumers, once after the creation of brand awareness has incurred. This chore is the main ingredient in creating a positive and optimistic brand image. In addition, there are three essential facets established to brand image which establishes the base for dissimilar consumer response for dissimilar products. The elements are strength, favorability and uniqueness of brand associations. Having a positive brand image is important for outlining a target market, formatting a product's position, and evaluating market response e.g. Long run advertising of Nyquil's medicine of night time cough played a very important role in its positioning. Progressive positioning of Nyquil's has developed a different, strong and desirable image of the brand. The main feature of Nyquil's is that it was the only brand used by the people at night to cure their cough which made it unique. This medicine helps in curing the cough and along with that also proved beneficial in peaceful sleep which made a strong brand image of Nyquil's.

Despite the acknowledged and obvious importance of using brand extension as a marketing strategy for introducing new products relatively known about how consumers react to them, consumer reaction to brand extension appears to involve a categorization process in which the new product is judged [24]. According to [24] the most important task for advertisement is to identify the brand extension of the products and the image of

the brand amongst customers. He further said that one of the two basic categories of brand extension is function oriented and prestige oriented. Function oriented category visualizes the brand performance and its aspects such as sensor razors of Gillette are a functional-oriented brand, the reason is because customers are more focused on its functioning. While prestige oriented brand image shows the consumer reaction about the self expression for a product e.g. Mercedes 560 SL. Here consumers are more focused on the status and prestige which they get from it. Past researches also said that no matter either the consumers have prestige oriented approach or function oriented, the basic thing is how much the brands have high consistency and consumer's reaction about that consistency and its core features.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Branding is one of the significant functions of the company in the strategy of international marketing and strong brands play a major role in helping the companies to develop its identity in the market along with the ability to oppose the increasing power of retailer [25][4][26][27]. It also helps in providing a ground or basis for extension of a brand that helps in promoting the value and makes the position of the firm stronger [9]. According to [28] the importance of several issues depends on the extensive degree that how internationally the firm has extended and how it organized its operations in the international market, this phenomenon is supported by several examples in which some well-known companies e.g. Coca-cola and Proctor and Gamble have extended by leveraging their national products or brands internationally and in order to grow further they need to identify the likeness of the brand along with its extension at domestic level. Many past researchers examined that how the brand value which is incorporated in the brand and its worth can be stretch to other brands without diluting its value [9].

In the rising international industry where the market is full of advancements many times addition in brand take place in more than one markets operating nationally and during that period those people who are in practice must require knowledge for understandable and different personality of brand that usually be relevant and having worth in order to make sure the success in the long run, so this is obviously significant for personnel's who are at managerial level to have a sound understanding that additions in the brand or product which is aiming to the global market and also have an impact on various other markets would have diverse brand image [28][29][30]. In the life cycle of a brand that includes growth, expansion, scope and then adaptability, brand extension constantly theaters a vital share [31]. Companies around the world utilize the Brand image of parent brands in new markets and in introduction of new products in to the market e.g. Virgin Groups. Virgin is originally known for publishing and retailing of popular music. Therefore when company decided to launch their existing product in new durable markets, they used their prior reputation of the company. Virgin started as a

Music company and in current they are known for Businesses such as well reputed financial advisors, airlines, and Cold drink manufacturers [32].

Earlier researches showed that the opinion to move the original brand towards addition or extension is generally influenced with the customer's belief of match between extension and personality of brand, though it seems that addition in the brand raise the image of the parent brand, so there must be expectations of a suitable connection that will have an impact on the personality of a brand that ultimately affects the brand image and similar is the case in reverse that is brand image can provide positive and negative grounds for extension in existing brand [9][33][34][4][35]. Precisely best connection of addition in the brand and basic brand shows that addition is considered appropriately in regard to the parent brand and similarly miss match or miss connection will automatically shows miss appropriation in addition and with that of its parent brand [36][37][38]. Many researches in the recent years on consumer evaluation of brands and brand extension has attracted marketers to observe and embark interest in as how brand image can help a company to launch an extension of the existing successful brand by observing the consumer's perception and attitude towards brand extension of a specific brand. The initial research was done by [9] by designing a model to evaluate the consumer brand evaluation. According to conclusion of the research study, strong consumers involvement with a specific brand of any kind can assist in a high evaluation of brand extension or it situations can also result in harmful evaluations. If the parent brand is enjoying a good reputation and is well positioned, than acceptability of brand extension in a market is amplified. Furthermore, it is also observant that parent brands provides or arranges a stronger base for a more lucrative acceptance of their extensions [9].

A second research was conducted by [40] They opted for a similar methodology and hypothesis analysis as [9]. It is observed that relevancy occurs in some results while other remains dissimilar. According to their conclusion the association between the difficulties resulting due to creation of a product class of the extension and the attitude towards the extension was not significant. Though if the parent brand seeming quality is high then consumer's attitude towards recognition of product extension is high. The conclusion also provide sustenance to the results from the [9] study that is there are positive associations and consumer's attitude towards extension when considering a fit between a parent brand product class in comparison with the extension's product class.

A third research study was done by [40] This study is another extension replication of [9] study. The authors were keen in testing of results of both researches administered on consumer brand evaluation. According to the findings of the study which concludes that the two factors, which makes the association related to brand extension in a consumer's mind, are the perceived quality and the perceived fit of a parent brand. The research study conclusions did not provide substantial provisions to support [9] concept of consumers

favoring the concept of 'easy to make extension'. Many others has contributed in similar manner by projecting light on the increasing number of huge extensions in brand which depicts that the affiliations related to product are influenced by extensions in brand [41][42][43].

In Pakistan numerous researches has been conducted in the field of brand awareness Packaged Milk Industry in Pakistan and effect of brand extension on parent brand along with consumer's perspective measured in various studies [45]. This study is an initiative to lifts up a concept in a way in which Brand image influence on the additions into the brand amongst the consumers of Peshawar can be observed, by identifying the attitude of consumers towards brand extension in a brand depending on their perceptions of the brand's image is the domain area of the study.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collection

Data collection has two main types such as primary data and secondary data which can be defined as the data collected for the first time for a particular purpose is called primary data and the data collected from different sources for the purpose of taking help is known as secondary data.

Primary data is collected from the students of 5 different universities situated in KPK region of Peshawar who were the respondents of this study. For the purpose of collecting data convenience sampling procedure was used because of limitations of time and other constraints.

B. Instrument

The study is mainly focused on primary data. To collect the primary data questionnaires has been use, which is comprised of 18 questions relating to three different companies such as Nestle, Toyota and PTCL if they launch their new brands in the market than what would be the brand image of consumers in their mind about the parent brand of these companies.

C. Cronbach's Alpha

Cronbach's alpha is a technique to measure the internal consistency or one may say check the reliability of the instrument (Questionnaire). The Cronbach's alpha values between 0 and 1. In case of observing the effect of brand image of the parent brand on consumer's attitude towards brand extension in Peshawar region, the value of Cronbach's Alpha is .674. If the value of the Cronbach's alpha is near or more than 0.7, this means that all the variables have adequate reliabilities [46]

D. Sample Size

The sample size selected was 200 for this study based on five different educational institutions presented by a sample size of 40 each per institution. Great care has been put for equal representation of both genders. These institutions are mainly located in Peshawar.

E. Data Analysis Method

The data was recorded and analyzed with the help of SPSS software by using binomial and chi- square test.

F. Theoretical Framework

G. Research Hypothesis

H1: Positive image of a Parent Brand has a positive and direct influence on brand extension attitude

H2: Positive parent brand image will result in initial positive image of the extended brand

IV. ANALYSIS

A. Binomial Test

Binomial test is applied because in questionnaire there are two choices Yes and No in order to know about the brand image of respondents about three different companies and their attitude towards the extension of parent brand.

Table 1: Binomial Test

		Category	N	Observed Prop.	Test Prop.	Asymp. Sig. (1-tailed)
N1	Group 1	Yes	192	1.0	.7	.000 ^a
	Group 2	No	8	.0		
	Total		200	1.0		
N2	Group 1	Yes	191	1.0	.7	.000 ^a
	Group 2	No	9	.0		
	Total		200	1.0		
N3	Group 1	Yes	194	1.0	.7	.000 ^a
	Group 2	No	6	.0		
	Total		200	1.0		
N4	Group 1	Yes	170	.9	.7	.000 ^a
	Group 2	No	30	.2		
	Total		200	1.0		
N5	Group 1	No	39	.2	.7	.000 ^{a,b}
	Group 2	Yes	161	.8		
	Total		200	1.0		
N6	Group 1	Yes	97	.5	.7	.000 ^{a,b}
	Group 2	No	103	.5		

	Total		200	1.0		
T7	Group 1	Yes	194	1.0	.7	.000 ^a
	Group 2	No	6	.0		
	Total		200	1.0		
T8	Group 1	Yes	188	.9	.7	.000 ^a
	Group 2	No	12	.1		
	Total		200	1.0		
T9	Group 1	Yes	179	.9	.7	.000 ^a
	Group 2	No	21	.1		
	Total		200	1.0		
T10	Group 1	Yes	123	.6	.7	.006 ^{a,b}
	Group 2	No	77	.4		
	Total		200	1.0		
T11	Group 1	Yes	101	.5	.7	.000 ^{a,b}
	Group 2	No	99	.5		
	Total		200	1.0		
T12	Group 1	Yes	119	.6	.7	.001 ^{a,b}
	Group 2	No	81	.4		
	Total		200	1.0		
P13	Group 1	Yes	195	1.0	.7	.000 ^a
	Group 2	No	5	.0		
	Total		200	1.0		
P14	Group 1	Yes	188	.9	.7	.000 ^a
	Group 2	No	12	.1		
	Total		200	1.0		
P15	Group 1	Yes	141	.7	.7	.473 ^a
	Group 2	No	59	.3		
	Total		200	1.0		
P16	Group 1	Yes	142	.7	.7	.412 ^a
	Group 2	No	58	.3		
	Total		200	1.0		
P17	Group 1	No	95	.5	.7	.000 ^{a,b}
	Group 2	Yes	105	.5		
	Total		200	1.0		
P18	Group 1	No	110	.6	.7	.000 ^{a,b}
	Group 2	Yes	90	.5		
	Total		200	1.0		

- a. Based on Z Approximation.
b. Alternative hypothesis states that the proportion of cases in the first group $< .7$.

By seeing the results of binomial test all the results are significant except T10, P15 and P16. Since three brands have taken, one is from FMCG'S, one is from specialty goods and one is from service industry. It can be observed that majority of the consumers agreed from the fact that if they are satisfied with the parent brand than most probably they will prefer any brand extension launched under the umbrella of the parent brand. Although in T10 the results are significant but the margin is low so it means that consumers are not optimistic on brand extension and in P15 consumers do not perceive a positive image about the brand but still agree to use an extended brand launched under the umbrella of parent brand. In P16 consumers have bad image of brand when it comes to services.

B. Chi-Square Test:

Chi-square test is used for the purpose of cross tabulation of different questions to check their relationship. The results are summarized below:

Table 2.1: Chi-Square Tests (for cross tabulation of question N3 and N4)

Pearson Chi-Square	1.631 ^a	1	.202		
Continuity Correction ^b	.485	1	.486		
Likelihood Ratio	1.300	1	.254		
Fisher's Exact Test				.222	.222
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.622	1	.203		
N of Valid Cases ^b	200				

When considering cross tabulation of question 3 and question 4 it is observed that the results are insignificant and it means that the null hypothesis is accepted so it means that if there is any brand extension done under the umbrella of parent brand, consumers would have positive image regarding it.

Table 2.2: Chi-Square Tests (for cross tabulation of question N3 and N5)

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	3.666 ^a	1	.056		
Continuity Correction ^b	1.936	1	.164		
Likelihood Ratio	2.904	1	.088		
Fisher's Exact Test				.090	.090
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.647	1	.056		
N of Valid Cases ^b	200				

When considering cross tabulation of question 3 and question 5 it is observed that the results are insignificant and it means that the null hypothesis is accepted so it means that parent brand has a positive image when brand extensions is done in its umbrella.

Table 2.3 Chi-Square Tests (for cross tabulation of question N3 and N6)

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.006 ^a	1	.940		
Continuity Correction ^b	.000	1	1.000		
Likelihood Ratio	.006	1	.941		
Fisher's Exact Test				1.000	.630
Linear-by-Linear Association	.006	1	.941		
N of Valid Cases ^b	200				

When chi-square test was run on question 3 and question 6 the results were insignificant and it means that null hypothesis were accepted that is the parent brand has a positive image when brand extension is done in its umbrella.

Table 2.4 Chi-Square Tests (for cross tabulation of question T8 and T11)

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.505 ^a	1	.220		
Continuity Correction ^b	.863	1	.353		
Likelihood Ratio	1.531	1	.216		
Fisher's Exact Test				.248	.177
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.497	1	.221		
N of Valid Cases ^b	200				

When chi-square test was run on question 8 and question 11 the results were insignificant and it means that null hypothesis were accepted that is the parent brand has a positive image when brand extension is done in its umbrella.

Table 2.5: Chi-Square Tests (for cross tabulation of question T8 and T12)

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.478 ^a	1	.489		
Continuity Correction ^b	.151	1	.698		
Likelihood Ratio	.470	1	.493		
Fisher's Exact Test				.551	.344
Linear-by-Linear Association	.476	1	.490		
N of Valid Cases ^b	200				

When chi-square cross tabulation test was run on question 8 and question 12 the results were insignificant because the significance level is above .05 and it means that null hypothesis were accepted that is the parent brand has a positive image when brand extension is done in its umbrella.

Table 2.6: Chi-Square Tests (for cross tabulation of question P16 and P17)

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	23.244 ^a	1	.000		
Continuity Correction ^b	21.764	1	.000		
Likelihood Ratio	23.892	1	.000		
Fisher's Exact Test				.000	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	23.128	1	.000		
N of Valid Cases ^b	200				

Table 2.7: Chi-Square Tests (for cross tabulation of question P16 and P18)

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	6.437 ^a	1	.011		
Continuity Correction ^b	5.667	1	.017		
Likelihood Ratio	6.582	1	.010		
Fisher's Exact Test				.012	.008
Linear-by-Linear Association	6.405	1	.011		
N of Valid Cases ^b	200				

When observing cross tabulation of question 16 and question 18 the results are insignificant which shows that initial brand image will result in initial positive image of the extended brand.

In observing the results from table 1 that is binomial test and table 2.7 the results are insignificant with by only 12% which is not sufficient in proving H2. Although H2 is accepted but results is unclear because margin is very low only .12%.

V. CONCLUSION

The present study helps in understanding that how positive brand image affects the consumers attitude towards the extended brand of that company means if consumer's have a good brand image and reputation then automatically the extended brand will more likely to be accepted and similarly on the other hand unfavourable brand image results in the dislikness of people towards the extended product. Furthermore, it is observed that if the consumers of Peshawar have a good brand image than they will automatically opt for extended brand and the companies can also enjoy positive brand image as it will provide the initial positive image for the extended brand and brand loyalty. Results shows that it varies from industry to industry and has a great impact on FMCG'S and specialty goods but not in service industry such as telecommunication that's why H2 is rejected because the results were not up to the desired level and H1 is accepted.

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